

GREEN SCENT

SMART CITIZEN EDUCATION
FOR A GREEN FUTURE

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D3.6 – GreenSCENT Platform demonstrator

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Deliverable Leader	Engineering Ingegneria Informatica (ENG)
Deliverable Coordinator	Vladimiro Scotto di Carlo (ENG) – vladimiro.scottodicarlo@eng.it
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1.1. Author

Author name	Organization Acr.	E-mail
Vladimiro Scotto di Carlo	ENG	vladimiro.scottodicarlo@eng.it

1.2. Contributors

Contributor name	Organization Acr.	E-mail

1.3. Reviewers

Reviewers name	Organization Acr.	E-mail
Joe Berwick	RST	head@royalschool.ro
Manfred Mudelsee	CRA	mudelsee@climate-risk-analysis.com

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Editor address data	Name: Vladimiro Scotto di Carlo Partner: ENG Address: Torre Saverio Isola C1 Centro Direzionale, 80143 Napoli Phone: +393479022570 Email: vladimiro.scottodicarlo@eng.it
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1.7. Acronyms

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CPU	Central Processing Unit
GiB	Gibibyte, 2 ³⁰ byte (not to be confused with Gigabyte)
EBS	Elastic Block Store, cloud block storage for virtual machines on Amazon cloud platform
PU	Public Document
UI	User Interface
vCPU	Virtual CPU
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WebGL	Web-based Graphics Library
WP	Work Package

2. Introduction

2.1. Deliverable Aims and Objectives

The Deliverable D3.6 is a digital demonstrator. It is therefore a piece of software that provides specific features to users that has been developed and made available for project activities.

So this document does not constitute the deliverable, but it is a companion document that explains the technology, architecture and main functions of the demonstrator.

2.2. Project Overview

GreenSCENT – Smart Citizen Education for a Green Future – is a research and innovation project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under Grant Agreement N° 101036480.

The primary objective of GreenSCENT is to support the implementation of Green Deal policies by engaging EU citizens, particularly young people, in the co-creation, testing, and validation of a European Multidisciplinary Competence Framework that encompasses the main thematic areas of the EU Green Deal. The project aims to foster acceptance and uptake of the Green Deal through a multi-stakeholder participatory approach and measure its effectiveness in terms of awareness, skills, and implicit attitudes, which are crucial for real behavioural change.

The main founding pillars of the GreenSCENT project are as follows:

- **Citizen Engagement:** Within the project, citizen engagement is considered a driver for change. Actively involving citizens in policymaking improves the effectiveness, quality, and uptake of policies and decisions addressing complex challenges at both global and local levels, ranging from climate change to welfare redesign, territorial development, or public service provision. When citizens are involved and feel included in the creation of innovations, rather than merely being recipients, it becomes easier to ensure broad acceptance of these innovations.
- **Active Experimentation:** Active observation, data collection, and open innovation can enhance understanding and increase acceptance. By promoting engagement and hands-on actions, individuals are motivated to participate and feel involved in addressing environmental problems primarily caused by human activities. GreenSCENT will offer various comprehensive "demonstrators" that allow students and citizens to apply the proposed competency framework, encouraging them to engage with science and their behaviour. This way, they can observe, understand, and evaluate the impact of their actions on the planet.
- **European Youth:** The youth of the European Union is crucial for promoting knowledge and information about the Green Deal and the importance of adopting green behaviours. Young EU citizens can disseminate this information to their peers both in and out of school, as well as to their families. As they grow, they can become professionals driving change in the workforce, various industries, political, and social processes, all towards a green perspective for the planet's protection. Educational institutions like schools and universities play a vital role in this process. GreenSCENT plans to showcase its demonstrators in various settings, including schools, universities, and non-formal education settings, such as Open Innovation Challenges and Citizen Engagement initiatives, across different educational levels.
- **Involvement of Vulnerable Groups:** It is important to involve vulnerable groups, including migrants, refugees, people with disabilities, the elderly, and those living in rural areas, in both discussions and

practical measures concerning the Green Deal. The European Union's "united in diversity" philosophy cannot be achieved if these groups are excluded. Respect for diversity, inclusion, and democratic participation are fundamental EU principles, and GreenSCENT will ensure these are upheld. Considering the changes in education post-COVID-19, new methods of engaging people are necessary, and digital accessibility is crucial. Creating accessible content is essential to reach and motivate people while minimizing the risk of dropping out of education. GreenSCENT will involve different user groups in designing and validating proposed solutions and will adopt accessibility standards and cross-cultural approaches in developing any analog or digital demonstrators supporting the GreenSCENT Competence Framework.

- **GreenSCENT Competence Framework: Acceptance and Adoption:** The GreenSCENT project aims to involve EU citizens in increasing awareness and acceptance of the Green Deal growth plan. In addition to citizens, the project will engage potential users and stakeholders of the Competence Framework, such as experts, activists, educational providers, and employers. This engagement is necessary to ensure the broad adoption of the GreenSCENT Competence Framework beyond the project's lifetime. The framework can be used as a tool for designing and implementing educational initiatives both inside and outside the classroom. It can also facilitate the integration of environmental-related competencies in human resources and talent management enterprise processes.
- **Additional Competences Beyond Climate and Environment:** The project will involve citizens, particularly students, in activities that aim to test and validate the proposed competence framework. These activities will help individuals develop various competencies beyond just climate and sustainability knowledge. For instance, they will be challenged in areas such as science education, digital competences, and soft skills like creative thinking, problem-solving, team working, project planning, and design. These transversal and complementary competencies will positively impact both their personal and professional capacities, as well as their understanding of climate and environmental challenges.

3. General Information about Demonstrator

3.1. General Architecture

The GreenSCENT web platform has been designed as a seamless pipeline that can effectively store and manage various types of multimedia content, including video, photos, documents, and data, all of which are generated by or made available by the users of the platform.

This document is focused on the overall web interface and on the tools that are accessible only by a standard web browser (no mobile app), that are the Interactive Documentary Tool and the Citizen Journalism Tool.

"Interactive Documentary" is the webtool that enables the creation of immersive and interactive experiences; users can enrich a background photos or video (including 360° immersive pictures or footage) stored in the platform with additional elements. The tool provides a wide range of elements to overlay on the background videos/photos, including images, HTML links, 2D videos, and text. For each element, the user can define properties that specify its visual appearance and events that define interactive actions to trigger during playback (e.g., displaying an image when the element is clicked).

The Citizen Journalism tool is a web interface for creating and managing environmental reports. It can be some way considered the web counterpart of the Environmental Monitoring App (see D3.4) with more advanced administration features dedicated to administrators.

Overall, this document aims to provide users with a comprehensive understanding of the GreenSCENT web platform's interface, enabling them to use it effectively and efficiently.

Figure 1 provides a summary of the complete GreenSCENT platform, highlighting the key functional elements and their interrelationships. The architecture includes:

- The Storage and Distribution Facility (at the centre of the architecture);
- The Environmental Mobile APP;
- The Interactive Documentaries Tool;
- The Citizen Journalism Tool;
- The Administration Interface (dedicated to the general management of the entire platform).

Figure 1 – GreenSCENT Platform Overall Architecture

The GreenSCENT web/mobile platform, including the Web Admin interface, the Web User interface, and the Environmental Monitoring App, stands as a **robust web application that can be accessed through all common web browser** (Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, Safari, or others **supporting the HTML 5 standard and WebGL**). Crafted using the MERN stack (MongoDB, Express, React, Node), an open-source middleware stack, this platform facilitates the development of web and mobile interfaces that interact with a complex backend system.

Figure 2 – MERN Stack

To ensure a cohesive and effective system, the platform aligns itself with the widely accepted **three-tier architecture convention**, encompassing a Presentation Layer (frontend interface), an Application Layer (business logic), and a Database Layer. This architectural framework enhances user experience by assigning distinct functions to each tier, allowing for an intuitive and smooth interaction within the system.

Figure 3 – Three-tier Architecture Convention

3.2. Hardware Requirements for the Overall Platform

The backend part (Application Layer and Database layer) has been deployed on a cloud server under the responsibility of ENG. The server is a virtual machine on the Amazon AWS cloud infrastructure. The venue of the server farm is located in Milan and all the cloud resources are inside EU territory.

The server used is part of the t3 family (general purpose workloads based on 2nd generation Intel Xeon Platinum 8000 series processor). The specific instance allocated for the project is t3.xlarge (4vCPU, 16 GiB). The Operative System is Oracle Linux 8.5. Currently the server has 300 GB SSD disk on EBS.

Hardware characteristics can be increased/improved as needed. For instance, the number of vCPU or the RAM of the instance, or the disk space.

3.3. System Requirements for Users

A laptop with a modern browser (a recent version of Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, or others that support the HTML 5 standard and WebGL) and a fast internet connection of at least 30 Mbps is strongly recommended.

4. Main Features

4.1. Platform General Features

4.1.1. Login

Feature	
Description	How to access to the web platform with the institutional login credentials
Tutorial	<p>Go To http://greenvrse.net</p> <p>Click on the <p>On this page, users are required to provide the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Username in the "EMAIL" field (beware, this field is case sensitive, even though mail addresses are not). - Password in the "PASSWORD" field. - Institution name from the "SELECT INSTITUTION" dropdown list. <p>After the login the sections of the main landing page will be all enabled and the avatar of the user is shown on the ribbon at the top right corner</p>

4.1.2. Registration of New Users

Feature	
Description	How a new user can register to the platform
Tutorial	<p>By clicking on the "Register now" text link displayed on the login web page,</p> <p>users can access the registration form as shown in the figure below.</p>

The form requires users to fill in

- nickname,
- email,
- password,
- confirmation of the password.

Additionally, users must select their institution from the dropdown list and read and agree to the disclaimer by checking the appropriate box.

Once users have completed the registration form, they should press the "REGISTER" button to submit their request.

After submitting their registration request, users must wait for the administrator to verify and approve their request. Once the administrator approves or rejects the request. If their request is approved, they can access the portal and enjoy its features. However, if the user is rejected, they will not be able to access the portal.

Feature

Description

How an administrator can approve/reject a new user

Tutorial

This feature is only for the administrator of an institution..
After the login the sections of the main landing page will be all enabled and the avatar of the user is shown on the ribbon at the top right corner.
The administrator now must click on the SETTINGS button,

And on the USERS tab

The administrator will see all the users of the institution registered to the platform. The ones yet to be approved will be shown in red.

Clicking on the red pen, the administrator sees a dialog that allows the approval (or rejection) of the user.

4.1.3. Change Language

Feature	
Description	How to change the language of the web platform
Tutorial	<p>The user can change the language of the web interface. This can be done from any point of navigation even before authentication. Supported languages are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CATALAN - ESPANOL - ENGLISH - ITALIAN - GREEK <p>More languages could be added in future. To change language Click the world icon on the top navigation bar (visible at any point of navigation)</p> <p>Select the preferred language from the dialog</p>

4.1.4. Home Page Main Features

Feature	
Description	The main features of the home page
Tutorial	<p>A logged-in user can see the home page with all the sections active and accessible.</p> <p>The four main sections are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CREATE: it shows all the pieces of content that can be used to create an interactive documentary and allows the access to Interactive Documentary tool - CITIZEN JOURNALISM: it allows the visualization of all the reports coming from the territory that have been inserted in the platform through the Environmental Monitoring app. - ALL MEDIA: it shows all the multimedia content that have been inserted in the platform by the users belonging to the cultural institution - EXPLORE: it shows all the interactive documentaries that have been created (in the CREATE section) for the cultural institution.

4.1.5. Add a New Video Photo Background to the Platform

Feature	
Description	How to add a new photo to the platform. They can be standard flat photos/videos or 360 equirectangular
Tutorial	<p>The procedure is specific for high quality photos or videos that can be used as background for an interactive documentary. For other kind of media files see next paragraph.</p> <p>After login</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enter the CREATE section, clicking on the specific panel of the home page.

- Select the photo/video file from your local computer (supported formats are png, jpeg, mp4/H264, m4a/H264 for photos and videos).

- Now the mandatory fields will be automatically filled in. You can modify them and fill in the ones still empty. We strongly advise you to give a significant name to the resource (default value is the name of the file) and to check the rights (default choice is CC0, but many other options are possible)
- If the media file is a 360 photo or video the 360 trigger must be set to "360". Default "2D" value is for flat photo/video

- Press the SAVE button

- The new resource should appear as a card in the CREATE section in the top left corner of the list

4.1.6. Add a New Media File to the Platform

Feature	
Description	How to add a generic media file to the platform
Tutorial	<p>The procedure is generic for photos, videos, audio tracks, documents. Supported formats are: "png", "mp4", "mp3", "m4a", "jpg", "gif", "jpeg", "pdf", "doc", "ppt", "pptx", "txt", "xlsx", "docx", "json", "xls", "basis", "ktx2"</p> <p>After login</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enter the ALL MEDIA section, clicking on the specific panel of the home page. <div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Click on the + floating button

- Press the button **UPLOAD** in the dialog box

- Select the file from your local computer (supported formats are png, mp4, mp3, m4a, jpg, gif, jpeg, pdf, doc, ppt, pptx, txt, xlsx, docx, json, xls, basis, ktx2).

- Now the mandatory fields will be automatically filled in. You can modify them and fill in the ones still empty. We strongly advise you to give a significant name to the resource (default value is the name of the file) and to check the rights (default choice is CC0, but many other options are possible)

- Press the **SAVE** button

- The new resource should appear as a card in the ALL MEDIA section in the top left corner of the list

4.1.7. Use of Filters in CREATE/ALL MEDIA Section

Feature	
Description	How to manage the filters in CREATE section The CREATE section shows all the items that can be used as backgrounds to create an interactive documentary. Filters are defined in the interface to select items according to some specific criteria
Tutorial	After login Enter the CREATE section, clicking on the specific panel of the home page.

The CREATE section has:

- An horizontal filters bar containing a search box and other filters about rights, geolocation, sorting filters
- A vertical filters bar containing filters by type

HORIZONTAL BAR

Search	Search by text
	JUST user's items / ALL ITEMS If ON the interface shows just the items that belong to (that have been created by) the user
AZ	ORDER by alphabetic criteria, AZ/ZA according to the title
	ORDER by creation time (Form most recent to least or viceversa)
	MAP filter If ON shows only items with geographical coordinates on a map
	RIGHTS filter Filters according the rights associated to the items. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CC0 - CC-BY-* - COPYRIGHT

	<p>VERTICAL BAR</p> <p>Filters according to the media type:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 360 images - 2D (standard flat) images - 360 videos - 2D (standard flat) videos
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Feature	
Description	<p>How to manage the filters in ALL MEDIA section</p> <p>The ALL MEDIA section shows all the media files stored in the platform. Filters are defined in the interface to select items according to some specific criteria.</p>
Tutorial	<p>After login</p> <p>Enter the ALL MEDIA section, clicking on the specific panel of the home page.</p>

	Search	Search by text
		JUST user's items / ALL ITEMS If ON the interface shows just the items that belong to (that have been created by) the user
		ORDER by alphabetic criteria, AZ/ZA according to the title
		ORDER by creation time (Form most recent to least or viceversa)
		MAP filter If ON shows only items with geographical coordinates on a map
		RIGHTS filter Filters according the rights associated to the items. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CC0 - CC-BY-* - COPYRIGHT
VERTICAL BAR Filters according to the media type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 360 images - 2D (standard flat) images - Audio - 360 videos - 2D (standard flat) videos - Documents 		

4.2. Interactive Documentaries Tool

4.2.1. Create a New Documentary

Feature	
Description	The procedure to create a new interactive documentary
Tutorial	<p>After login</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enter the CREATE section, clicking on the specific panel of the home page. <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 10px; margin: 10px 0;"> </div> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select the background (photo or video) among the ones shown in the page (default visualization shows only the pictures that belong

to the user, if you want to see all the backgrounds available deselect the specific filter on the filter bar)

- Once you have chosen the background select the specific button on the right down corner of the card

- The dialog box will show all the documentaries that have been created on that background. Click on the + button to create new one

- Insert the name of your new documentary and click OK

- Now you are in the tool that allows the creation of the documentary

4.2.2. Edit a Documentary

Feature	
Description	How to improve an existing documentary
Tutorial	After Login

- Enter the EXPLORE section, clicking on the specific panel of the home page.

- Select the documentary (you can edit only your own documentaries) and click the button on the right down corner of the card

- Now you are in the tool that allows the edit and the modification of the documentary

4.2.3. Add an Image Hotspot

Feature	
Description	How to add an Image hotspot to an interactive documentary
Tutorial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open the documentary in the Interactive Documentary tool has shown before , and then clicking on the desired position on the video/image displayed in the preview area (don't drag it from the menu to the preview area, it wouldn't work). Users have the flexibility to adjust the position of the hotspot by clicking and dragging it to the desired location. - Once the hotspot is added to the background video/image, users can view and modify its properties in the right panel as shown in the figure.

The following list shows the properties that can be set for the hotspot.

	<p>INFO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Name</i>: modify the default name for the Hotspot (optional). - <i>Description</i>: insert a short description (optional)

		<p>POSITION</p> <p>This property allows to change the image position acting on the three-dimensional coordinates X, Y, Z. Only advanced users. The best way to change the position of the hotspot is to use drag and drop.</p>
	to load an image resource by choosing one of those proposed in the list of resources stored in the platform <p>The formats supported are jpg, png, gif</p>	

		<p>SIZE</p> <p>This option is to modify the size of the hotspot. It's possible to use the slider or a numeric field. They both represent the width of the image. The ratio between height and width is always maintained.</p>
		<p>VIEW OPTIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Show Hotspot: Default value true. If set to false (unchecked) the hotspot is invisible and only an action on another hotspot will make it visible (see Drive Hotspot action) - Blinking. It will make the hotspot blink. 3 blinking speeds available - OnBackground/Fixed on screen. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. OnBBackground, the hotspot is fixed to the 360 background b. Fixed on screen, the hotspot is on foreground, always visible

4.2.4. Add a Video Hotspot

Feature	
Description	How to add a Video hotspot to an interactive documentary
Tutorial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open the documentary in the Interactive Documentary tool has shown before

- The left panel, presents the following hotspot types:

- The "2D Video" hotspot can be added to the preview area by clicking on the icon , and then clicking on the desired position on the video/image displayed in the preview area (don't drag it from the menu to the preview area, it wouldn't work). Users have the flexibility to adjust the position of the hotspot by dragging it to the desired location.
- Once the hotspot is added to the background video/image, users can view and modify its properties in the right panel as shown in the figure.

The following list shows the properties that can be set for the hotspot.

		<p>INFO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- <i>Name</i>: modify the default name for the Hotspot (optional).- <i>Description</i>: insert a short description (optional)

		<p>POSITION</p> <p>This property allows to change the video position acting on the three-dimensional coordinates X, Y, Z. Only advanced users. The best way to change the position of the hotspot is to use drag and drop.</p>
	to load a video resource by choosing one of those proposed in the list of resources stored in the platform. <p>The formats supported are mp4/h264, mkv/h264</p>	

		<p>SIZE</p> <p>This option is to modify the size of the hotspot. It's possible to use the slider or a numeric field. They both represent the width of the video. The ratio between height and width is always maintained.</p>
		<p>COVER</p> <p>Only for advanced users</p>

		<p>PLAY OPTIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LOOP. The video will be played in loop - AUTOPLAY. The video will start automatically - STOP BACKGROUND VIDEO. While the hotspot is running the background video (if the background is a video) is stopped
		<p>VIEW OPTIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Show Hotspot: Default value true. If set to false (unchecked) the hotspot is invisible and only an action on another hotspot will make it visible (see Drive Hotspot action) - OnBackground/Fixed on screen. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> OnBackground, the hotspot is fixed to the 360 background Fixed on screen, the hotspot is on foreground, always visible

4.2.5. Add an Audio Hotspot

Feature	
Description	How top add an Audio hotspot to an interactive documentary
Tutorial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open the documentary in the Interactive Documentary tool has shown before

- The left panel presents the following hotspot types:

- The "Audio" hotspot can be added to the preview area by clicking on the icon , and then clicking on the desired position on the video/image displayed in the preview area (don't drag it from the menu to the preview area, it wouldn't work). Users have the flexibility to adjust the position of the hotspot by dragging it to the desired location.
- Once the hotspot is added to the background video/image, users can view and modify its properties in the right panel as shown in figure.

The following list shows the properties that can be set for the hotspot.

		<p>INFO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Name</i>: modify the default name for the Hotspot (optional). - <i>Description</i>: insert a short description (optional)
		<p>POSITION</p> <p>This property allows to change the audio position acting on the three-dimensional coordinates X, Y, Z. Only advanced users. The best way to change the position of the hotspot is to use drag and drop.</p>

	to load an audio track resource by choosing one of those proposed in the list of resources stored in the platform <p>Format supported are mp3, aac</p>	
		<p>SIZE</p> <p>This option is to modify the size of the hotspot. It's possible to use the slider or a numeric field. They both represent the width of the audiotrack hotspot. The ratio between height and width is always maintained.</p>

		<p>COVER Only for advanced users</p>
		<p>PLAY OPTIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LOOP. The video will be played in loop - AUTOPLAY. The video will start automatically <p>STOP BACKGROUND VIDEO. While the hotspot is running the background video (if the background is a video) is stopped</p>

		<p>VIEW OPTIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Show Hotspot: Default value true. If set to false (unchecked) the hotspot is invisible and only an action on another hotspot will make it visible (see Drive Hotspot action) - OnBackground/Fixed on screen. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. OnBackground, the hotspot is fixed to the 360 background b. Fixed on screen, the hotspot is on foreground, always visible

4.2.6. Add a Text Hotspot

Feature	
<p>Description</p>	<p>How to add a Text Hotspot to an interactive documentary</p>
<p>Tutorial</p>	<p>Open the documentary in the Interactive Documentary tool has shown before</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The left panel, presents the following hotspot types:

- The "Text" hotspot can be added to the preview area by clicking on the icon , and then clicking on the desired position on the video/image displayed in the preview area (don't drag it from the menu to the preview area, it wouldn't work). Users have the flexibility to adjust the position of the hotspot by dragging it to the desired location.
- Once the hotspot is added to the background video/image, users can view and modify its properties in the right panel as shown in figure.

The following list shows the properties that can be set for the hotspot.

		<p>INFO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Name</i>: modify the default name for the Hotspot (optional). - <i>Description</i>: insert a short description (optional)
		<p>POSITION</p> <p>This property allows to change the image position acting on the three-dimensional coordinates X, Y, Z Only advanced users. The best way to change the position of the hotspot is to use drag and drop.</p>

		<p>COLOR To set the color of the panel (not the text) It's possible to choose:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The color - The transparency (alpha channel)
		<p>FONT It's possible to choose the appearance of the font:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - BOLD, ITALIC, Underlined, color - Font - Font size - The text

		<p>SIZE</p> <p>This option is to modify the size of the hotspot.</p> <p>There are two sliders, one for the height of the panel, one for the width</p>
		<p>VIEW OPTIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Show Hotspot: Default value true. If set to false (unchecked) the hotspot is invisible and only an action on another hotspot will make it visible (see Drive Hotspot action) - Blinking. It will make the hotspot blink. 3 blinking speeds available - OnBackground/Fixed on screen. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. OnBBackground, the hotspot is fixed to the 360 background b. Fixed on screen, the hotspot is on foreground, always visible

4.2.7. Set an OpenLink Action on a Hotspot

Feature	
Description	<p>An Image (or a Text) hotspot can be made sensible to onClick/onTap even from a user.</p> <p>This event can launch the specific OpenLink action that drives the opening of an external webpage in a panel on the top of the documentary (in foreground) or in another tab of the browser in background)</p>
Tutorial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open the documentary in the Interactive Documentary tool as shown before - Insert a new Image/Text hotspot or select an existing one - On the right menu, select the Event panel

- Click on the OnClick/OnTap Event and select the **Open Link** action

- Click on the button immediately below the action

- The dialog shown allows to insert the external website that can be launched by clicking the hotspot

- The user has to type the address of the link (including http:// or https://...), select the option **New Window/Full Screen** and press OK. Use of the buttons on the right of the text box is only for advanced users.
New Window option is the one that allows the opening of the website in background on a new tab of the browser
Full screen option will set the website to be opened in foreground in a panel before the documentary. This option could not work with all the websites as some of them are set to prevent the opening inside another website (in this case the documentary). So if this option won't work for a specific website, it will be necessary to fall back on the other option (New Window).

4.2.8. Set a DriveHotspot Action on a Hotspot

Feature	
Description	<p>An Image (or a Text) hotspot can be made sensible to onClick/onTap even from a user.</p> <p>This event can launch the specific DRIVEHOTSPOT action that can drive the appearance/disappearance of other hotspots in the documentary.</p> <p>So in this scenario there is a piloting hotspot (the one that must be clicked/tapped) and some (one or more) target hotspots that can be driven. To drive a hotspot means that if it is invisible, it becomes visible and viceversa. So the piloting hotspot can work to turn on and off the targets on the scene.</p>
Tutorial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open the documentary in the Interactive Documentary tool as shown before - Insert a new Image/Text hotspot or select an existing one - On the right menu, select the Event panel - Click on the OnClick/OnTap Event and select the DRIVE HOTSPOT action <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The dialog shown allows to insert the other hotspots (the targets) that can be driven by clicking/tapping the first hotspot (the pilot).

- The user has to select the hotspots that they want to be driven and click OK button.

So after this configuration there is a piloting hotspot (the one that must be clicked/tapped) and some (one or more) target hotspots that can be driven. To drive a hotspot means that if it is invisible, it becomes visible and vice versa. So the piloting hotspot can work to turn on and off the targets on the scene.

4.2.9. Set a Jump Action on a Hotspot

Feature	
Description	<p>An Image (or a Text) hotspot can be made sensible to onClick/onTap even from a user.</p> <p>This event can launch the specific JUMP action that allows the user to jump toward another scene or documentary. This is the fastest way to implement a path containing different environments.</p>
Tutorial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open the documentary in the Interactive Documentary tool as shown before. - Insert a new Image/Text hotspot or select an existing one - On the right menu, select the Event panel - Click on the OnClick/OnTap Event and select the JUMP action <div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Click on the button immediately below the action

- The dialog shown allows to select the background the user can jump to

- After clicking on the chosen background, the user can select a specific documentary or jump to the "naked" background

- The next options are just for advanced users.

- Please just press ok

4.2.10. Save a Documentary

Feature	
Description	How to save a documentary
Tutorial	<p>After doing all the modifications and the edits, the user can save them clicking on the SAVE icon on the top of the preview area</p>

4.2.11. Watch a Preview of a Documentary

Feature	
Description	How to have a preview of the documentary while still working on it
Tutorial	<p>After saving a documentary, a user can have a fast preview of the result without leaving the tool clicking on the PREVIEW icon at the top of the preview area. The documentary in its current form will be displayed in another tab of the browser.</p>

4.3. Explore Section

4.3.1. Watch a Documentary (Explore Section)

Feature	
Description	The EXPLORE section on the landing page shows all the documentaries that have been created. From there you can watch/share them.
Tutorial	<p>After Login</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enter the EXPLORE section, by clicking on the specific panel of the home page. <p style="font-size: small; margin-top: 5px;">This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036480. ©2022 Greenscent. All right reserved.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select the documentary and click on the central part of the card (on the picture)

- On the opening dialog click on the VIEW button

The documentary will be visualized in another tab of the browser

4.3.2. Share the Link of a Documentary

Feature	
Description	The EXPLORE section on the landing page shows all the documentaries that have been created. From there you can watch/share them.
Tutorial	After Login - Enter the EXPLORE section, by clicking on the specific panel of the home page.

The screenshot shows the 'EXPLORE' section of the GreenSCENT platform. At the top, there are four main categories: CREATE, CITIZEN JOURNALISM, ALL MEDIA, and EXPLORE. The EXPLORE category is highlighted with a red box. Below this, there is a search bar and navigation icons. A grid of documentary cards is displayed. One card is highlighted with a red box, and a hand cursor is pointing at the 'SHARE' button on the card. Below the grid, a 'SHARE LINK' dialog box is shown, containing the following information:

IDENTIFIER: documentarytry

CC0 <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>

<https://cuhet-backend2.net/H360/use?processId=documentarytry&id=64ec9fabefe3f22a38e5023d&resType=IMAGE3&domain=64ec9c37> **COPY**

- Select the documentary and click on the SHARE button on the card

The dialog will show the link to share the documentary. The COPY button can copy it in the user's clipboard automatically

4.3.3. Generate the QR Code of a Documentary

Feature

<p>Description</p>	<p>The EXPLORE section on the landing page shows all the documentaries that have been created. From there you can watch/share them and also create a QR code to allow a direct access to the documentary</p>
<p>Tutorial</p>	<p>After Login</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enter the EXPLORE section, by clicking on the specific panel of the home page. <p>EXPLORE</p> <p>documentarytry 28/08/2023, 13:28:36 UTC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The dialog shows the QR code that can be downloaded on the user's computer as well

4.4. Citizen Journalism Tool

4.4.1. Access to Citizen Journalism Tool

Feature	
Description	How to access to Citizen Journalism section
Tutorial	<p>After login In the landing page click on the Citizen Journalism section</p> <p>The start page for Citizen Journalism will be visualized.</p>

The page displays on the map and on a list of cards all the reports that are in APPROVED and RESOLVED state.

4.4.2. Add New Report

Feature	
Description	How to add a new report in the Citizen Journalism web interface
Tutorial	<p>Usually, the addition of a new report is made from Environmental Monitoring mobile app, but Citizen Journalism web app can be useful to the purpose as well.</p> <p>After login, enter the Citizen Journalism section.</p> <p>Click on the + button floating on the bottom left corner of the interface.</p>
	<p>Fill in the dialog CREATE REPORT</p>

- Insert the **TITLE** of the report (3-15 characters)
- Insert the **DESCRIPTION** (a detailed text that explains the situation) of the report (8-350 characters)
- Set the tags (semantic classification of the report) among the available categories (one is mandatory and it is the best option, more than one is possible)
- Set the severity between the three possible values (LOW, MEDIUM, HIGH)
- Click the to use a resource that is already in the platform. At every click, a new attachment can be added up to three items. There must be at least one picture attached to the report. One of the pictures must be the cover (there is a checkbox that can be set on the photos, at least one is set by default)

- Set the position of the report by clicking on the pinpoint

- Click on OK on the map dialog and on SAVE in the CREATE REPORT

The new report has been added to the list and the map but it is still in TO BE APPROVED state

4.4.3. Approve/Reject a Report

Feature	
Description	How to change state and APPROVE/REJECT a report
Tutorial	Only the Administrator can approve a report, standard users are not allowed to. After login, the administrator enters the Citizen Journalism section.

- Select the report to approve in the list of cards, click on the card menu in the right upper corner and click on the CHANGE STATUS icon

- In the foreground dialog, the administrator must set the new status RESOLVED add a note (optional) and press SAVE

4.4.4. Detail of a Report

Feature	
Description	How to visualize the details of a report
Tutorial	After login, any user can visualize the detail of any report in APPROVED state <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enter the Citizen Journalism section. - Select the report to visualize in the list of cards, click on the card menu in the right upper corner and on the DETAIL icon

- A dialog box with all the details is shown

The pictures/videos attached can be visualized in full size by clicking the eye icon on the thumbnails.

4.4.5. Social Interaction on a Report (CROWDSOURCING)

Feature	Description
Description	Social interaction on a report
Tutorial	<p>Users can add their updates on the reports that are in the APPROVED state After login,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enter the Citizen Journalism section. - Select the report to interact with and click OPENCHAT button <div style="text-align: center; margin: 10px 0;"> </div> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The dialog shows all the interactions that have currently been done by other users: comments, updates, links etc - Click on the MODIFY button to add a new comment

Only reports in APPROVED state can be further commented. For reports in SOLVED state users can see the past interaction, but not add anything else.

4.4.6. Solve a Report

Feature	
Description	How to change state and SOLVE a report
Tutorial	<p>The creator/owner of a report and/or the administrator can put any APPROVED report in the following RESOLVED/SOLVED state.</p> <p>After login, the user/administrator enters the Citizen Journalism section.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select the report to approve in the list of cards, clicks on the card menu in the right upper corner and click on the CHANGE STATUS icon

In the foreground dialog, the administrator must set the new status APPROVED (or REJECTED), add a note (optional) and press SAVE

4.4.7. Delete a Report

Feature	
Description	How to delete a report from the list
Tutorial	<p>Administrators can delete reports in any state (TO BE APPROVED, APPROVED, REJECTED, SOLVED)</p> <p>The creator (owner) of a report can delete it only before approval (TO BE APPROVED)</p> <p>After login, the user/administrator enters the Citizen Journalism section.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Select the report to delete it from the list of cards, click on the card menu in the right upper corner and on the DELETE icon (note that the DELETE ICON is active only if the user has the permission to execute the deletion according to the criteria listed before)

REPORT

test 30/10/2023, 09:04:26 UTC

TO BE APPROVED

Lecture about water ... 07/10/2023, 11:49:39 UTC

APPROVED

↓

REPORT

test 2 30/10/2023, 09:38:29 UTC

RESOLVED

test 30/10/2023, 09:21:07 UTC

REJECTED

- A confirmation dialog is shown.

REMOVE test 2

Are you sure?

NO YES

- After confirmation the deletion is complete